

UNFIRED THE GREEN CONSTRUCTION MATERIAL CLAY

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CO2 SAVINGS

If a house is built in unfired clay instead of reinforced concrete and tiles, we have estimated that the CO₂ emission is reduced by more than 90%.

The main saving is found in the process of making the materials. Producing reinforced concrete will have an emission of 53 kg CO₂ pr. ton reinforced concrete and producing tiles will give an emission of 79 kg CO₂ pr. ton yellow tiles. There is no significant emission of CO₂ in the process of making the unfired clay.

House of clay			House of concrete and tiles		
Purpose	Machine		Purpose	Machine	
Earthwork	Excavator + truck	24 kg CO ₂	Earthwork	Excavator+ truck	23 kg CO ₂
Clay and sand	Excavator	22 kg CO ₂	Reinforced concrete	Kiln	2648 kg CO ₂
			Yellow tiles	Kiln	1291 kg CO ₂
House of clay, totally		46 kg CO ₂	House of concrete, totally		3962 kg CO ₂
All other necessary equipment and thermal isolation are assumed the same for both houses and are not included					
SAVINGS		99 %			

We have only calculated the differences in producing of the houses. For example the emission for the roof and the machines needed for producing the house is almost the same for both houses.

There is also a great saving in demolition of the house. The unfired clay can be recycled just as it is.

Cut down the CO₂ emission - build green!

COMPRESSION STRENGTH

A materials strength parameters describes how resistant the material is to compression and tensile.

In Denmark the material is exposed for changes in the weather. Therefore the relative humidity is a parameter for our strength.

For the tests we used a cylinder (ø100/200 mm) that is compressed until it breaks. The load is noted and converted to the compression strength.

The arrangement for the compression strength test, the cylinder is ø100 mm/ 200 mm.

A test sample after it breaks.

Measured compression strength for our test samples and the standard deviation.

Compression strength as a function of the relative humidity. It shows that the tile mixture has less strength than the gravel mixture.

EXPERIENCES SALTOFTEVÆNGET

In Svebølle (DK) they built a student accommodation in 1987/88 made with following details:

The outer wall is made of 600mm stamped clay, 200mm hard isolation batts and a surface of chalk rendering. The ground deck is made of reinforced concrete with 1,5m leca stones underneath. Upon the ceiling there is 200mm isolation and the roof is shaped, so the solar panels are placed optimal. The partition walls are made by stamped clay.

When they built the clay house in 1987/88, the biggest problem was the organization of the project. Especially because the construction work were executed by the young students, without experience.

In general the experiences with the clay house were good, and they now have a different type of building, where the students can live cheap - only 1500 DKR pr. month.

The pictures show the building in Svebølle from the outside.

The floor plan of the building in Svebølle. As you can see the walls are quite thick (800 mm).

MOISTURE BUFFERING

The moisture buffering effect is a materials ability to master the variations in the relative humidity. A high value of the moisture buffering ability means that the material has a great ability to create a good indoor environment.

The practical moisture buffering effect for unfired clay is measured according to the NORDTEST method. The clay sample is inserted in a climate chamber which controls the temperature and the relative humidity. The sample mass is measured continuously.

Stamped clay house, from the inside.

Experimental setup; climate chamber

The practical moisture buffering effect for the clay/gravel mixture: 1,2g/(m²%RF)

The practical moisture buffering effect for the clay/tile mixture: 0,8g/(m²%RF)

PROCESS METHOD

Using pisé for constructions put the clay mixture into the formwork and stamp it.

The clay needs to be without bigger lumps and plant leftovers. If the clay has high moisture content, shrinkage will appear. To prevent cracks, you can insert joints in the wall, so you can control the cracks. The clay can also be improved when mixed with cement, chalk or fiber reinforcement.

Clay is a very weather sensitive material; the building period is limited to April/May-August/September. 4 men can stamp 1m³ each in 8 hours. This means that it will take about 15 days to stamp a normal 100m² house.

The layers in pisé

THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY

The heat conductivity λ [W/mK] can be determined by the instrument ISOMET: Heat transfer analyzer. The probe is placed upon the test sample and connected to the instrument.

The heat loss coefficient (U) for the house is proportional to the heat conductivity.

Experimental setup of ISOMET: Heat transfer analyzer.